

MODERN METHODS OF TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF CHRONIC GASTRITIS

Haydarov Navro'zbek Furqat o'g'li

Asian International University, Bukhara, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15225930>

Abstract. Prevalence of chronic gastritis has markedly declined in developed populations during the past decades. However, chronic gastritis is still one of the most common serious pandemic infections with such severe killing sequelae as peptic ulcer or gastric cancer. Globally, on average, even more than half of people may have a chronic gastritis at present. *Helicobacter pylori* infection in childhood is the main cause of chronic gastritis, which microbial origin is the key for the understanding of the bizarre epidemiology and course of the disease. A life-long and aggressive inflammation in gastritis results in destruction (atrophic gastritis) of stomach mucosa with time (years and decades). The progressive worsening of atrophic gastritis results subsequently in dysfunctions of stomach mucosa. Atrophic gastritis will finally end up in a permanently acid-free stomach in the most extreme cases. Severe atrophic gastritis and acid-free stomach are the highest independent risk conditions for gastric cancer known so far. In addition to the risks of malignancy and peptic ulcer, acid-free stomach and severe forms of atrophic gastritis may associate with failures in absorption of essential vitamins, like vitamin B12, micronutrients (like iron, calcium, magnesium and zinc), diet and medicines

Key words: gastric cancer, gastritis, *Helicobacter pylori*, peptic ulcer.

СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ И ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ГАСТРИТА

Аннотация. Распространенность хронического гастрита заметно снизилась в развитых популяциях за последние десятилетия. Тем не менее, хронический гастрит по-прежнему является одной из самых распространенных серьезных пандемических инфекций с такими тяжелыми смертельными последствиями, как язвенная болезнь или рак желудка. В среднем в мире даже более половины людей могут иметь хронический гастрит в настоящее время. Инфекция *Helicobacter pylori* в детстве является основной причиной хронического гастрита, микробное происхождение которого является ключом к пониманию странной эпидемиологии и течения заболевания. Пожизненное и агрессивное воспаление при гастрите приводит к разрушению (атрофический гастрит) слизистой оболочки желудка со временем (годы и десятилетия). Прогрессирующее ухудшение атрофического гастрита впоследствии приводит к дисфункциям слизистой оболочки желудка. Атрофический гастрит в конечном итоге заканчивается постоянной ацидозной кислотой в желудке в самых крайних случаях. Тяжелый атрофический

гастрит и ацидоз желудка являются самыми высокими независимыми рисками рака желудка, известными на сегодняшний день. В дополнение к рискам злокачественности и язвенной болезни, ацидоз желудка и тяжелые формы атрофического гастрита могут быть связаны с нарушениями всасывания основных витаминов, таких как витамин B12, микроэлементов (таких как железо, кальций, магний и цинк), диеты и лекарств

Ключевые слова: рак желудка, гастрит, *Helicobacter pylori*, язвенная болезнь.

Introduction

Chronic gastritis is one of the most common life-long, serious and insidious illnesses in human beings. One may estimate that more than half of the world population have this disease in some degree and extent, indicating that even many hundreds of millions of people worldwide may have chronic gastritis in a form or other. The significance of chronic gastritis as a serious disease is largely underrated in clinical practice, even though the role of gastritis in the pathogenesis of ordinary peptic ulcers and gastric cancers is obvious. One may estimate that millions of premature deaths may occur annually worldwide due to cancer and ulcer as sequelae of the chronic gastritis. Chronic gastritis appears either as nonatrophic or atrophic form. They are forms and phenotypes of gastritis which represent different stages of a same life-long disease.

The morphological appearances of gastritis published are very similar. worldwide, i.e., chronic gastritis is seemingly, with its sequelae, one and same disorder throughout the world.

Chronic gastritis has been known and studied since the early decades of the 20th century but received more attention not until 1982 after discovery of the *Helicobacter pylori* by Warren and Marshall. It has become clear that the bacterium is the cause of gastritis in an overwhelming majority of the cases, a possible exception being a gastritis of the autoimmune origin.

Consequently, it has become evident that chronic gastritis can be cured with eradication of *H. pylori*, resulting in normalization of the gastric mucosa, at least in cases in which the gastritis is not developed to atrophic (atrophic gastritis) end stages. Even though the main outlines of chronic gastritis are well known, several unanswered questions occur still. We do not know, for example, the significance of autoimmunity or genetics in the development and progression of chronic *H. pylori* gastritis. The molecular mechanisms and the role of environmental factors, like diet, and the role of other microbes than *H. pylori* on the course of chronic gastritis, are largely unknown. We cannot precisely predict either in whom the chronic gastritis will certainly progress to atrophic end stages and to killing sequelae, or in whom it will not. This uncertainty is also the case regarding the details by which the gastritis accomplishes the appearances of peptic ulcers or gastric cancer.

We know, however, that without the presence of a coexisting chronic gastritis or atrophic gastritis, ordinary peptic ulcers or stomach cancers are rare. Over the years, most of these studies have been published in this journal.

Etiology

Chronic gastritis is a multistep, progressive and lifelong inflammation. It begins usually in childhood as a simple chronic (“superficial”) mononuclear inflammation with co-existence of an acute (“active”) neutrophilic inflammation of varying degree. Gastritis progresses stepwise, within years and decades, to atrophic gastritis that is characterized by a loss of normal mucosal glands either in antrum or corpus (and fundus), or in both. At present, the increase of the age-specific prevalences of gastritis by age is more pronounced and abrupt in the developing than in the developed populations, i.e., the prevalence of gastritis in young age-groups, or even in childhood, is much more than 52% in developing populations, whereas this prevalence in developed population is typically much less than 50%. The loss of mucosal glands in atrophic gastritis is replaced with a growth of new immature glandular and epithelial elements; that is, with glands of intestinal type (“intestinal metaplasia (IM)”), resembling glands and epithelium in colon and/or small bowel, and/or with pyloric type (“pseudopyloric metaplasia”), resembling pyloric glands and epithelium from which the G cell (gastrin cell) are disappeared. In frames of the evolution, the highly differentiated glands, epithelium and cells are destroyed in atrophy (atrophic gastritis) and the lost glands are replaced by glands and epithelium with immature intestinal properties. The chronic inflammation associates with a neutrophilic inflammation, the intensity of this acute and “active” component of gastritis being most likely dependent on the cytotoxicity of the *H. pylori* strain. The more cytotoxic the strain is, the more active, and, obviously, more aggressive is the chronic gastritis. The most aggressive forms of chronic gastritis are those which result most likely in advanced stages of atrophic gastritis, i.e., are forms of *H. pylori* gastritis with highest likelihood to progress to the end-stage atrophy. The annual risk of progression of chronic gastritis from one step to the next one is estimated to be 3–4% on average. It is estimated further that ~50% of patients with chronic gastritis (and *H. pylori* infection) will get atrophic gastritis of some grade and extent during the life-time. In some 5% of the infected people, atrophic gastritis will get a severe and advanced stage. A slow extension of *H. pylori* gastritis from a pure antral phenotype to forms that affect also the corpus and fundus (“atrophic pangastritis”, multifocal atrophic gastritis” or “corpus predominant gastritis”) tends to be a common. This proximal (pyloro-cardial) spread and the gradual worsening of atrophic gastritis associate with marked changes in morphology and function of the stomach mucosa. The affections interfere stomach functions by causing particularly failures in secretion of hydrochloric acid and intrinsic factor from oxyntic glands in corpus atrophy, and failures in

synthesis and secretion of gastrin-17 from antral G cells in antral atrophy. A severe atrophic gastritis that is strictly limited to antrum alone is obviously quite rare. On the other hand, an advanced atrophy that occurs in corpus alone, or occupies both antral and corpus compartments simultaneously, is a relatively common phenotype of chronic gastritis (in up to 5% of people with gastritis), in the Northern Europe at least. The long-term follow-up studies suggest that, along with the upward extension of *H. pylori* gastritis, the antral mucosa may even heal. Due to the loss of oxyntic glands and parietal cells in corpus atrophy, the extension of atrophic gastritis to corpus and fundus results in a life-long and permanent hypo- or achlorhydria. Subsequently, due to a low intragastric acidity, the initial *H. pylori* infection may, in turn, spontaneously fade and may finally heal in cases with an advanced atrophy as is demonstrated with serology tests in the follow-ups. Along the progression of chronic non-atrophic gastritis to atrophic phenotypes, manifold coincidental pathogenetic processes, even carcinogenic ones, are potentially triggered on, which phenomena in sc. “Correa cascade” may finally contribute to processes that link the chronic gastritis with such extreme sequelae as cancer.

Epidemiology and the birth cohort phenomenon

The observations from population studies on chronic gastritis may empower some fundamental conclusions concerning the epidemiology of chronic gastritis and its sequelae.

Chronic gastritis is still a relatively common disease, also in developed countries even though its prevalence has markedly declined, this decline being parallel with a decline of the *H. pylori* prevalence. It is conceivable that practically everyone, even in developed countries, had *H. pylori* gastritis some 100 years ago, whereas the prevalence may be now less than 50% on average. *H. pylori* gastritis is acquired in early childhood in most of the cases, the phenotype of gastritis being then a harmless and symptom-free simple chronic mononuclear (“superficial”) inflammation. The severe symptomatic sequelae of chronic gastritis will appear not until in last decades of the life, and tend arise in subjects with the advanced end stages lesions. After discovery of *H. pylori*, it became evident that the understanding of the epidemiology of *H. pylori* infection is the key for the understanding of the epidemiology of chronic gastritis and its sequelae as well. As being initially a pandemic pediatric bacterial infection, the epidemiological characteristics of chronic gastritis and its sequelae (peptic ulcer and gastric cancer) follow the same “pandemic” principles as those of *H. pylori* infection by itself. Socioeconomics and environmental hygiene are inevitably the most important background factors in transmission of *H. pylori* infection worldwide, these socioeconomic factors being, thereby, the background factors also in epidemiology of chronic gastritis and its sequelae. Socioeconomic status in childhood, environmental and family-bound hygiene, household density, cooking habits, etc., are plausible factors that determine the likelihood to acquire the *H. pylori* infection in the childhood.

Improvements in these conditions diminish the likelihood to get the infection, or to transmit the infection further, by a gastro-oral route most likely. A decline of the infection rate in childhood at the family level will inevitably result, with time, in a decline of the prevalence of both *H. pylori* gastritis and its sequelae also in the whole population on average. The infection rate in childhood and the age-specific prevalence of *H. pylori* gastritis are high in the “old” birth cohorts born decades earlier than the prevalence in the “young” birth cohorts born more recently and in whom the infection rate of *H. pylori* at childhood is low. Thus, the mean prevalence of gastritis at the population level reflects the average of the prevalences of chronic gastritis in different birth cohorts, and the mean rate of *H. pylori* infection at pediatric age. The epidemiology of stomach cancer incidence, and the epidemiology of stomach cancer mortality, follow the principles of the “birth cohort phenomenon” and show similar global “pandemic” characteristics as the case is with the *H. pylori* gastritis. The incidence rate of gastric cancer (or peptic ulcer) is and will be low in the “young” birth cohorts in whom the incidence of *H. pylori* gastritis is low and in whom the stomach mucosa remains healthy through the whole life-span. Instead, the prevalence, incidence and mortality for peptic ulcer or gastric cancer are high, and remain high, in the old cohorts as long as the cohorts live

Autoimmune chronic gastritis

Although *H. pylori* is ultimately the major cause (in more than 90% of the cases) of gastritis, a chronic mononuclear inflammation (gastritis) without an ongoing *H. pylori* infection, but occurring with a severe atrophic corpus gastritis and achlorhydric stomach, and with co-existence of auto-antibodies against parietal cells (proton pump) and/or intrinsic factor, is a well established entity. It is uncertain, however, whether this gastritis of “autoimmune” type is an independent disorder or whether the *H. pylori* triggers autoimmune reactions on in some liable individuals with an ordinary *H. pylori* infection. It is possible that the initial *H. pylori* infection may pass spontaneously out when the atrophic gastritis is developed to severely atrophic and achlorhydric stage, giving, thereby, a false impression of a pure autoimmune etiology of the disease. A gastritis linked with the autoimmune phenomena may anyhow be more progressive and faster in course than the pure *H. pylori* gastritis. In connection with autoimmunity, and in persons with a liability to autoimmune diseases (autoimmune thyreoiditis, diabetes, etc.), the progression of *H. pylori* gastritis to atrophic phenotypes may be markedly destructive, possibly resulting easily and quickly in achlorhydria and in total atrophy of gastric corpus and fundus. Cases with severe atrophic corpus gastritis with autoimmune characteristics and with acid-free stomach even in childhood have been described in the medical literature.

Influences on stomach physiology

A long-lasting (life-long) chronic and active inflammation cannot be harmless and will result in destruction of stomach mucosa via several mechanisms which may interact with renewal, growth, integrity, differentiation and function of the gastric epithelium. Numerous abnormal expressions (up- and down-regulations) of functional and regulatory genes, gene mutations, epigenetic alterations, variable appearances of cytokines or tissue growth factors occur in the regulatory tissue processes of gastric mucosa and epithelial cells in connection with *H. pylori* gastritis. Some of the alterations are reversal, may appear even at early stages of inflammation, but may particularly accumulate with time in premalignant conditions, such as atrophy and IM, and seem to be extremely common and manifold in precancerous (dysplasia or intraepithelial neoplasia) and malignant lesions. Corpus atrophy leads ultimately to failures in the secretion of hydrochloric acid and intrinsic factor. In acid-free and atrophic stomach, due to the impairment in secretion of intrinsic factor, absorption of the essential vitamins, like vitamin B12, are severely failed. Malabsorption and subsequent long-lasting and permanent deficiency of vitamin B12 can impair the metabolism of methionine, homocysteine or folate, and may be, thereby, a mechanism which contributes to the appearances of epigenetic DNA damages via impairments in function of the methylation cycle in epithelial cells. Dietary metabolism and absorption of micronutrients, like iron, calcium, magnesium and zinc, or absorption of some medicines (e.g., dipyridamol, some iron formulations and anti-fungal medicines like fluconazole or itraconazole, thyroxin and atazanovir) are impaired in acid-free stomach too **Cancer and peptic ulcer**

Gastric cancer and peptic ulcer diseases (excluding NSAID ulcers) are the most serious diseases linked with the chronic *H. pylori* gastritis. A successful eradication of the *H. pylori* prevents ulcer recurrences but may also prevent cancers. In spite of the associations of peptic ulcers and cancer with *H. pylori* gastritis, there also are remarkable dissimilarities regarding these links. Peptic duodenal ulcers (DU) occur typically in people with non-atrophic *H. pylori* gastritis but are infrequent or absent in subjects in whom the gastritis has progressed to atrophic forms in corpus, and in whom the stomach is, subsequently, hypochlorhydric. Gastric ulcers associate often, on the other hand, with the phenotypes of gastritis in which a marked atrophy and IM occur in antrum and incisura, and in which cases, the corpus mucosa may even be slightly atrophic but is never severely atrophic (and stomach is never achlorhydric). The stomach cancer, the intestinal type in particular, is seen in patients with a hypochlorhydric or achlorhydric stomach and may particularly occur in subjects with advanced stages of atrophy and IM in both antrum and corpus.

Gastric carcinogenesis is heterogeneous and extremely varied at the molecular level.

Even though the gene errors are plentiful, no specific or comprehensive molecular markers, gene errors or mutations have been found in cancer or in precancer lesions so far.

Although the two main histological types of stomach cancer, intestinal and diffuse one, are meaningful entities in clinical and morphological perspectives, and both being bound to a preceding or co-existing *H. pylori* gastritis, the types may not be fully distinct entities. In diffuse type, the background morphology is often a non-atrophic *H. pylori* gastritis, indicating that the carcinogenetic mechanisms in this cancer type may be linked more closely with the inflammation than are associated with the mechanisms that appear in atrophic gastritis or acid free stomach. In intestinal cancer type, on the other hand, the overt tumors or the precancer lesions associate often with a hypochlorhydric stomach, and with a marked atrophic gastritis, and with extensive IM in the underlying mucosa. Therefore, the carcinogenetic processes in this cancer type may be linked with mechanisms that arise in atrophic gastritis or are triggered on by a hypochlorhydric or acid-free stomach. diminish when the cancer risk rises, as the case is in the patients with advanced atrophic gastritis. The cancer risk may be, for example, high in subjects with a severe atrophic gastritis and acid-free stomach in whom there may even be no objective signs of an on-going *H. pylori* infection, i.e., in patients in whom the initial *H. pylori* infection is possibly passed out

Plasma biomarkers in diagnosis and screening of atrophic gastritis

Purification of stomach pepsinogens in the 70s, understanding of natural course of *H. pylori* infection unique innovations in microwell plate vertical measurement techniques and in development of ELISA tests with specific monoclonal antibodies have provided applications to use gastric biomarkers in noninvasive diagnosis and screening of atrophic gastritis from a simple blood sample. At present, these blood tests can be performed reliably in any laboratory and they do not need special arrangements. Several detailed and comprehensive reviews, consensus reports and guidelines on practical usage of the biomarker tests in the diagnosis of atrophic gastritis have been published previously in this and other medical journals. Several commercial radioimmunoassays and ELISA tests have been available for pepsinogen 1 and 2 for a quite long time. These tests have, however, limitations because they can be used in the diagnosis of atrophic corpus gastritis only. The serum levels of pepsinogens 1 and 2 do not give any hints of possible atrophic gastritis in gastric antrum where the atrophic and metaplastic alterations appear, however, first. A more complete test (GastroPanel) includes an assay of the plasma levels of G-17, in addition to the assays of pepsinogen 1 and pepsinogen 2, and includes also the *H. pylori* serology test. This test panel enables assessments of atrophy also in the gastric antrum and gives hints of intragastric acidity in addition to the information of possible corpus atrophy, and makes, therefore, the comprehensive OLGA classification possible.

Antral atrophic gastritis (loss of antral glands) is accompanied with a loss of antral G cell, which cell loss results in low plasma levels of both fasting and stimulated gastrin-17 (after a drink with protein powder, stimulation with bombesin (gastrin releasing peptide) or stimulation with proton pump inhibitor (PPI)). A low fasting plasma G-17 (1 pmol/l or less) indicates two options in practice. Either there is an advanced atrophic gastritis in the antrum (OLGA class III–IV) or the low G-17 is a result of a high intragastric acidity (low pH). Both options are indications for upper gi-endoscopy because of the cancer risk due to possible antral atrophy and because of the peptic ulcer risk due to hyperchlorhydria (high-acid output). The absence of H. pylori antibodies concomitantly with the presence of normal plasma levels of pepsinogen 1, with normal ratio of pepsinogen 1 to pepsinogen 2, and with normal plasma gastrin-17, providing that a possible PPI medication is controlled, is a test result that reliably suggests the presence of normal and healthy stomach mucosa (OLGA class 0). The risk of cancer and peptic ulcer in such “healthy” subjects is extremely low, practically nil. The risk of gastric cancer is, on the other hand, high (OLGA class III-IV) in subjects with low levels of fasting pepsinogen 1 (less than 30 microg/l), with low pepsinogen 1 to pepsinogen 2 ratio (lower than 3) and with high fasting gastrin-17 (above 6 pmol/l), The cancer risk is high in these patients irrespectively of whether the patient has or does not have an on-going H. Pylori infection. The atrophic gastritis is advanced and extensive in these cases, occupies the whole stomach mucosa (OLGA class IV), and the stomach is concomitantly acid free

Future trends and the healthy stomach initiative

Future trends and the healthy stomach initiative Even though the H. pylori gastritis is declining in prevalence, chronic gastritis will still be a remarkably frequent disease globally for several future decades. Due to the microbial origin and infectious background, and by the knowledges of epidemiology and natural course of chronic H. pylori gastritis, one can assume that this disease may finally disappear from the society, along with the improvements in hygiene and in socioeconomics. With these improvements, the risk to acquire H. pylori infection in childhood will decline. As the case is with tuberculosis, chronic gastritis may move in the future decades to periphery of the medical practice and significance, in developed countries at least. Consequently, peptic ulcers will be rare and gastric cancer will become an infrequent malignancy. In the youngest native citizens in birth cohorts in western countries, some 92–100% of people already now have and will have a normal healthy stomach for their whole life-span, resulting finally in populations in which the exceeding majority of people have a healthy stomach and are, therefore, free of risks of peptic ulcer or stomach cancer. The attempts to maintain or to receive a healthy stomach to everybody will be an initiative and a goal in both future research and clinical practice.

REFERENCES

1. Saodat, A., Vohid, A., Ravshan, N., & Shamshod, A. (2020). MRI study in patients with idiopathic coxarthrosis of the hip joint. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(2), 410-415.
2. Axmedov, S. J. (2023). EFFECTS OF THE DRUG MILDRONATE. *Innovative Development in Educational Activities*, 2(20), 40-59.
3. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). ASCORBIC ACID: ITS ROLE IN IMMUNE SYSTEM, CHRONIC INFLAMMATION DISEASES AND ON THE ANTIOXIDANT EFFECTS. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 3(11), 57-60.
4. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). THE ROLE OF THIOTRIAZOLINE IN THE ORGANISM. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 9(5), 152-155.
5. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). HEPTRAL IS USED IN LIVER DISEASES. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 35(3), 76-78.
6. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2023). EFFECT OF TIVORTIN ON CARDIOMYOCYTE CELLS AND ITS ROLE IN MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION. *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 42, 255-257.
7. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). NEUROPROTECTIVE EFFECT OF CITICOLINE. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(1), 1-4.
8. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF TRIMETAZIDINE IN ISCHEMIC CARDIOMYOPATHY. *Journal of new century innovations*, 44(2), 3-8.
9. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ВСЕ ЭФФЕКТЫ ПРЕПАРАТА ИМУДОН. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 39-43.
10. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE EFFECT OF THE HEPARIN DRUG. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 34-38.
11. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF GLUCOCORTICOSTEROIDS IN PEDIATRIC PRACTICE. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 29-33.
12. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РОЛЬ ИНТЕЛЛАНОВОГО СИРОПА И ЦИАНОКОБАЛАМИНА В УЛУЧШЕНИИ ПАМЯТИ. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(2), 44-48.
13. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). TREATMENT OF POLYNEUROPATHY WITH BERLITHION. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 201-209.
14. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF ASCORIL IN BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 191-200.

15. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG ARTOXAN. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 182-190.
16. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF RENGALIN IN CHRONIC BRONCHITIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 116-123.
17. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF ALMAGEL DRUG IN GASTRIC AND DUODENAL WOUND DISEASE. *Ta'limning zamonaviy transformatsiyasi*, 4(1), 173-181.
18. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF CODELAK BRONCHO SYRUP IN CHILDREN'S PRACTICE. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 109-115.
19. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE AEVIT DRUG EFFECT. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 124-132.
20. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF ALCHEBA DRUG IN POST-STROKE APHASIA. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 132-138.
21. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF HYALURON CHONDRON DRUG IN OSTEOARTHRITIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(4), 139-145.
22. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). EFFECT OF SIMETHICONE DROP IN FLATULENCE. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 95-101.
23. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). BENEFITS OF BETADINE SOLUTION. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 116-122.
24. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). EFFECT INHALED GLUCOCORTICOIDS IN CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE AND BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *TADQIQOTLAR*, 31(1), 171-180.
25. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF VIGANTOL IN RICKETS. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 102-108.
26. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE VITAPROST DRUG RESULTS. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 109-115.
27. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF BISEPTOL DRUG IN URINARY TRACT DISEASE. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 14(1), 89-94.
28. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). PROPERTIES OF THE DRUG DORMIKIND. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 88-92.

29. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). IMMUNOMODULATORY FUNCTION OF DIBAZOL DRUG. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 83-87.
30. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). ADVANTAGES OF THE DRUG NERTRAL. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 98-101.
31. Эргашов, Б. К., & Ахмедов, Ш. Ж. (2024). ГИПЕРТОНИЧЕСКАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ ЭТИОЛОГИЯ. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 59-69.
32. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). HYPERTENSION, CLASSIFICATION AND PATHOGENESIS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 50-58.
33. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). YURAK ISHEMIYASI. STENOKARDIYADA SHOSHILINCH TIBBIY YORDAM. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 12-20.
34. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). HYPERTENSION ETIOLOGY. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 32-41.
35. Komilovich, E. B., & Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). CARDIAC ISCHEMIA. ANGINA NURSING DIAGNOSIS AND CARE. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 44-52.
36. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). IMPORTANT INDICATIONS OF THE DRUG WOBENZYM. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 29-32.
37. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE RESULTS OF THE EFFECT OF THE DRUG VALIDOL. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 19-23.
38. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). VIFERON USE IN CHILDREN. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 24-28.
39. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USE OF DUSPATALIN (MEBEVERINE HYDROCHLORIDE) IN GASTROINTESTINAL DISEASES. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(5), 93-97.
40. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ЭФФЕКТЫ СИРОПА ДЕПАКИНА (ВАЛЬПРОЕВАЯ КИСЛОТА). *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 148-152.
41. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG ALLOCHOL FOR CHRONIC CHOLECYSTITIS. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 133-137.

42. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). ВАЖНЫЕ СВОЙСТВА ПРЕПАРАТА ДЕ-НОЛ (субцитрат висмута). *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 143-147.
43. Jamshidovich, A. S., & Komilovich, E. B. (2024). SPECIAL FEATURES OF BUDECTON DRUG. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 14(2), 138-142.
44. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). ЭФФЕКТИВНОЕ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЕ ПРЕПАРАТА КЕЙВЕР. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 137-143.
45. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). USEFUL PROPERTIES OF THE DRUG YODOFOL. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 144-149.
46. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). FITOTERAPIYANING AKUSHER-GINEKOLOGIYADA ANAMIYATI. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 121-125.
47. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DRUG DOPROKIN. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 109-114.
48. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE EFFECT OF DOSTINEX ON THE BODY. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 115-120.
49. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ДЕЙСТВИЯ ПРЕПАРАТА КАНЕФРОН. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 138-143.
50. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ЭФФЕКТЫ ПРЕПАРАТА ИНДОЛ. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 126-131.
51. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). EFFECT OF ISMIZHEN DRUG ON BODY IMMUNITY. *Лучшие интеллектуальные исследования*, 15(2), 132-137.
52. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). POSITIVE EFFECTS OF THE DRUG CARCIL. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 127-131.
53. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). РЕЗУЛЬТАТЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ДЕЙСТВИЯ КАВИНТОНА. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 15(3), 132-136.
54. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). Современный Эффект Спрея Мометазон. *Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies*, 3(3), 62-65.
55. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE ROLE OF" SIMONTE PLUS" DRUG IN THE MODERN TREATMENT OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(5), 66-70.
56. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). FEATURES OF THE BIOMECHANISM OF THE DRUG LEVOMYCETIN (CHLORAMPHENICOL). *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(9), 298-301.

57. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE MOST IMPORTANT INDICATORS OF OMEGA 3 SUBSTANCE IN THE METABOLISM OF THE HUMAN BODY. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(10), 113-117.
58. Komilovich, E. B., & Khalimovich, M. N. (2024). CARDIAC ISCHEMIA. ANGINA CLINICAL FORMS AND DIAGNOSIS. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 70-78.
59. Komilovich, E. B. (2024). CORONARY HEART DISEASE. ANGINA EMERGENCY CARE. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(7), 235-242.
60. Komilovich, E. B. (2024). YURAK ISHEMIK KASALLIGI. STENOKARDIYANI DAVOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY TAMOYILLARI. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 3-11.
61. Jamshidovich, A. S. (2024). THE MOST IMPORTANT BENEFITS OF GINGER FOR THE HUMAN BODY'S IMMUNITY. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 4(11), 269-273.
62. Axmedov, S. (2024). THE SPECIFIC EFFECT OF THE DRUG "BAKLASAN" IN CEREBROVASCULAR DISEASES AND ITS PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE TODAY. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(12), 485-492.
63. Komilovich, E. B. Z. (2023). Coronary Artery Disease. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 3(12), 81-87.
64. Komilovich, E. B. (2024). CORONARY HEART DISEASE. ANGINA TREATMENT. *Journal of new century innovations*, 46(1), 95-104.
65. Komilovich, E. B. (2024). HYPERTENSION TREATMENT. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(7), 227-234.
66. Эргашов, Б. К. (2024). ИШЕМИЧЕСКАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ СЕРДЦА. СТЕНОКАРДИЯ ПРОФИЛАКТИКА. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 21-31.
67. Axmedov, S. (2025). ВАЖНЫЕ СВОЙСТВА ПРЕПАРАТА ЭСКУЗАН ПРИ СОСУДИСТЫХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯХ. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(1), 380-387.
68. Эргашов, Б. К. (2024). ГИПЕРТОНИЧЕСКАЯ БОЛЕЗНЬ ДИАГНОСТИКА. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 70-78.
69. Komilovich, E. B. (2024). HYPERTENSION DIAGNOSTICS. *ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ*, 38(6), 42-49.

70. Xusenovich, M. S., & Turapjanovna, Z. M. (2024). SEMIZLIKNING TURLI FENOTIPLARDA KARDIOMETABOLIK XAVF OMILLARINI TAQQOSLASH. *SO'NGI ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR NAZARIYASI*, 7(4), 112-116.
71. Husenovich, M. S., & Turabdjnovna, Z. M. (2024). STUDY OF DIURNAL PROFILE OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION IN DIFFERENT PHENOTYPE OBESITY. *образование наука и инновационные идеи в мире*, 43(1), 129-131.
72. Xusenovich, M. S. (2024, September). SEMIZLIKNI TURLI FENOTIPLARIDA YURAK QON-TOMIR KASALLIKLARINI KELIB CHIQISH XAVFI PROGNOZI. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 3, No. 26, pp. 15-18).
73. Xusenovich, M. S. (2024). O 'ZBEKISTONDA RESPUBLIKASIDA YURAK-QON TOMIR KASALLIKLARI TARQALISHI VA HOZIRGI KUNDAGI KO'RILAYOTGAN CHORA TADBIRLAR. *AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE*, 2(3), 79-82.
74. Xusenovich, M. S., & Allayarovich, A. A. (2024). O 'ZBEKISTONDA YURAK-QON TOMIR KASALLIKLARI TARQALISHI VA HOZIRGI KUNDAGI TENDENSIYASI. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 4(38), 54-57.
75. Ravshanovna, X. L. (2021, June). MINIMALLY INVASIVE METHODS OF TREATMENT OF DENTAL CARIES IN ADULTS. In " *ONLINE-CONFERENCES*" *PLATFORM* (pp. 118-119).
76. Axmedov, S. (2025). SPECIFIC PROPERTIES OF ROXERA DRUG IN CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASES. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(2), 472-479.
77. Axmedov, S. (2025). THE DRUG PHYSIOTENS, THE FEATURES OF THE DRUG AND ITS USE IN THE FIELD OF CARDIOLOGY, IN PATIENTS WITH HEAVY BODY WEIGHT. *Modern Science and Research*, 4(3), 350-358.